

**Federal Ministries of Education Compliance to Advertisement
for Solicitation Of Bids Guidelines in the Public Procurement
Act, 2007, Nigeria**

NJOKU, Hyacinth T., ABDULLAHI, Mohammed and AHMED, Uthman Omale

Department of Public Administration, Faculty of Administration,

Nasarawa State University, Keffi

mohammedabdul@nsuk.edu.ng: 08037867095

Abstract

Since the enactment of the Act in 2007, it has been observed that the public procurement implementation process is still faced with challenges in government Ministries, Departments and Agencies (MDAs). The observation made by Bureau of Public Procurement (BPP) through the Office of the Secretary to the Government of the Federation (SGF) in its Circular with reference: Ref.No.59858/S.11/VOL.II/332.It observed that publication for solicitation of bids in Federal Tender Journal and National Dailies by most MDAs of Federal Government exhibit poor compliance with the standard requirement for the solicitation of bids as stipulated in Section 16(6) of the Public Procurement Act, 2007. Based on these findings the study seeks to assess the extent of compliance, looking at the Federal Ministry of Education. The research adopted a descriptive survey method and used structured questionnaires and observation to collect the data for analysis. The data were collected from a sample of 400 respondents purposively drawn from the contractors, consultants and service providers of the Federal Ministry of Education Headquarters' projects, goods and services, staff of the BPP and Civil Society Organizations into procurement and budget monitoring in Nigeria. An analysis of the collected data revealed that the Federal Ministry of Education to large extent complied with maintaining of Notice Board for the public posting of procurement notices and solicitations, to a moderate extent complied with placing of advertisement in at least two National newspapers of general circulation and the Federal Tender's Journal the Request for Proposal (RFPs), to a large extent complied with placing advertisement on the BPP website the RFPs, but did not complied with placing advertisement on their official website the Request for Proposal (RFPs), and to a low extent complied with the required format of advertisements for

solicitation of bids submitted to the Editorial Board of the Federal Tender Journals. It recommended that the Federal Ministry of Education and other MDAs should build or rebuild its functional website to carry a webpage for its procurement matters and notices as required by the BPP Procurement Procedures and Manual and BBP should conduct a capacity training of its staff and staff of the Federal Ministry of Education and other MDAs on how draft RFPs following the guidelines provided by the BPP, among others.

Keywords: *Advertisement, Solicitation of Bids, Public Procurement Act.*

Introduction

The introduction of public procurement reforms in Nigeria was facilitated by the findings and recommendations of World Bank Country Procurement Assessment Report (CPAR) for Nigerian 1999. The report revealed that 60 kobo was being lost to underhand practices out of every one Naira (N1.00) spent by Government and that an average of ten Billion US Dollars (\$10b) was being lost annually due to fraudulent practices in the award and execution of public contracts (World Bank, 2000). The report recommends among others, the enactment of a procurement law to underpin the reforms being proposed. In a bid to implement the recommendations led to the setting up of the Budget Monitoring and Price Intelligent Unit (BMPIU), known as 'Due Process' in 2001, which is part of the broad government economic reform agenda. Due process implies that governmental activities and business can be carried out openly, economically and with emphasis on transparency without favouritism and corruptible tendencies (Ezekwesili, 2002). This was designed to ensure that rules and procedures for procurement are made in such a way as to be implementable and enforceable in the award and execution of Federal Government contracts and minimize open abuses to known rules, processes and standards in the award and execution of public sector contracts in Nigeria (BPP, 2007).

However, the Budget Monitoring and Price Intelligence Unit (BMPIU) is not a legal framework as recommended by the World Bank CPAR, (2000) It also faced with the of its inability to reduce corrupt practices as a result of collusion by public officials and the lack of clear role definitions and delineation for proper public procurement practices and ensure transparency, probity, accountability and openness (Adewole, 2014; Eze, 2015; Udoma and Belo-Osagie, 2012). In a bid to correct the anomalies and sustain the reforms, a Public Procurement Bill was articulated in 2003/2004 by the leadership of BMPIU led by Dr. Oby Ezekwesili and. The Public Procurement Bill was passed into law by the National Assembly on the 30th of May, 2007 and subsequently signed into law by the President on the 4th of June, 2007 as the Public Procurement Act 2007 (BPP Act, 2007). The purpose of the Act

is to ensure that all the public procurements are conducted in a manner that is transparent, competitive, professional, timely and equitable and based on the agreed guidelines, thresholds and standards to guarantee value for money in the public sector procurement system (Jacob, 2010).

Since the enactment of the Act in 2007 and the domestication of the Act by 24 states of the federation (Adewole, 2014), it is evident that the Act has come to stay in Nigeria. However, it is observed that the public procurement implementation process is still faced with challenges in government Ministries, Departments and Agencies (MDAs) such as inordinate delays in tender/order processing among others, and sometimes, contractors claim that they are even unaware of Federal Government Procurement notices or Tenders that are advertised in the national dailies or Federal Tenders Journal (Adebiyi, Ayo, and Adebiyi, 2010). This is corroborated by observation made by Bureau of Public Procurement (BPP) through the Office of the Secretary to the Government of the Federation (SGF) in its Circular with reference: Ref.No.59858/S.11/VOL.II/332, on the guideline for publication of advertisement in the Federal Tender Journal and National Dailies issued on the on 18th May, 2018 to all MDAs. It observed that publication for solicitation of bids in Federal Tender Journal and National Dailies by most MDAs of Federal Government exhibit poor compliance with the standard requirement for the solicitation of bids as stipulated in Section 16(6) of the Public Procurement Act, 2007. This affects the Standard Processing Time of procurement in MDAs resulting in project delay occasioned by the need to correct the publication before the process will start.

From the foregoing, the problem now is not the lack of a regulatory framework but rather that of poor implementation and non-compliance with the guidelines and regulations. Thus, the question is since the correction and clear stipulation of the guideline for publication of advertisement for solicitation of bid in the Federal Tender Journal and National Dailies by the BBP through the SGF in 2018, has the Federal Ministry of Education which is one of the Ministries with the highest Departments and Agencies, now comply with the guidelines as stipulated?

Objectives of the Study

In a broad perspective, this study seeks to assess the extent of compliance by Federal Ministry of Education with the Public Procurement Act, 2007 guidelines for solicitation of bids in the procurement process. Specifically, the study hopes to achieve the following objectives:

- I. To find out the extent Federal Ministry of Education complied with maintaining of Notice Board for the public posting of procurement notices and solicitations as

- stipulated in the Procurement Procedures Manual for public procurement in pursuant of the Public Procurement Act, 2007.
- ii. To ascertain the extent Federal Ministry of Education has complied with advertising in at least two National newspapers of general circulation and the Federal Tender's Journal the Request for Proposal (RFPs) as stipulated in the Procurement Procedures Manual for public procurement in pursuant of the Public Procurement Act, 2007.
 - iii. To discover the extent Federal Ministry of Education has complied with advertising in their official website and BPP website the Request for Proposal (RFPs) as stipulated in the Procurement Procedures Manual for public procurement in pursuant of the Public Procurement Act, 2007.
 - iv. To assess the extent the Federal Ministry of Education has complied with the required format of advertisements for solicitation of bids submitted to the Editorial Board of the Federal Tender Journals as stipulate in the SGF circular on guideline for publication of advertisement in the Federal Tender Journal and National Dallies.

Research Question

- i. To what extent has the Federal Ministry of Education complied with maintaining of Notice Board for the public posting of procurement notices and solicitations?
- ii. To what extent has Federal Ministry of Education comply with placing of advertisement in at least two National newspapers of general circulation and the Federal Tender's Journal the Request for Proposal (RFPs)?
- iii. To what extent has Federal Ministry of Education comply with placing advertisement in their official website and BPP website the Request for Proposal (RFPs)?
- iv. To what extent has Federal Ministry of Education comply with the required format of advertisements for solicitation of bids submitted to the Editorial Board of the Federal Tender Journals?

Literature Review Conceptual Framework Public Procurement

There are different scholarly views and definition of the term of procurement, each of which is operationally related to the content of discussion and application. Weele Van (2010) stated that procurement is the acquisition of goods, services or works from an outside external source. It encompasses the whole process of acquiring goods and/or services, thus it more than just buying of goods, works or services, as the definition may make it seem. It connotes the process of tendering, rather than buying of products directly from a seller. The Chartered Institute of Purchasing and Supply (CIPS), (2012) in

identifying the process gave the most succinct explanation, which is adopted in this study. It states that procurement is the business management function that ensures identification, sourcing, access and management of the external resources that an organization needs or may need to fulfil its strategic objectives. It does not deal with a single action or process. It covers the complete range of events from the identification of a need for a good or service through to its disposal or cessation. It exists to explore supply market opportunities and to implement resourcing strategies that deliver the best possible supply outcome to the organization, its stakeholders and customers.

The process of procurement when done by a government or applied to a government business is referred to as public procurement. That is, when goods and services are purchased by a public sector for a government, it is generally referred as public procurement. Pratyush (2009) put it as the process by which government and/ or its institutions buy inputs or contract services for vital public sector investments or function (Pratyush, 2009). According to Arrowsmith et al., (2011), it refers to the government's activity of purchasing the goods and services which it needs to carry out its functions. Accordingly, it entails the process of sourcing and acquisition of goods and services destined for the public sector (Bovis, 2007). It involves acquisition by contract, usually with appropriated funds, supplies, services, and interests in real property by and for the use of the government. The acquisition could be achieved through purchase or lease (Nash, Cibnic, Ralph & Nagle, 2006). According to Lysons and Farrington, (2006) it is the process of obtaining goods or services in any way, including borrowing, leasing and even force of pillage. There are three phases of the public procurement process; deciding which goods or services are to be bought and when (procurement planning); the process of placing a contract to acquire those goods or services which involves, in particular, choosing who is to be the contracting partner and the terms on which goods or services are to be provided; and the process of administering the contract to ensure effective performance (Arrowsmith et al., 2011). In this regard, public procurement systems refer to the aforementioned trio.

Ultimately, according to the Procurement Procedures Manual for Public Procurement in Nigeria, (2011) procurement is a function and a process responsible for obtaining resources (equipment, logistics, materials, supplies and services) required by an (public) organization to fulfill its core business and development programme. This may be done by purchase, lease or other legal means. Uneam and Mark (2015) opine that public procurement is the process by which government Ministries, Departments and Agencies (MDAs) and Parastatals, purchase goods and services from the private sector under specific rules and policies, usually encapsulated in the Public Procurement Act and

Procurement Manuals. A point worth emphasizing is that, public procurement, unlike private, is a business process inside a form of government. The items involved in public procurement range from simple goods and services such as cleaning services to large commercial projects, such as the development of infrastructure, including road, power stations and airports. Mupanduki (2012), notes that such goods and services are often acquired through a public procurement process whereby the government entity contracts with a private sector enterprise to furnish a particular good or service for a fee subject to legal terms and conditions contained in a contract.

Public Procurement Process and Approach: Advertisement for Solicitation of Bids

Procurement process involves several elements, including requirements determination, supplier research, value analysis, raising a purchase request, review phase, conversion to purchase order, contract administration, monitoring/evaluation of received order, three-way matching, payment fulfilment, and record keeping (Wan Lu, 2007; Emmett and Crocker, 2008; Kissflow, 2020). Public sector procurement process has a similar phase which starts with the identification of operational requirements that are determined and specified by the user and subsequently consolidated as a composite requirement for the procurement. The traditionally accepted objectives of procurement processes and approaches are to ensure that works are executed at the minimum cost that is consistent with the need to achieve a product of acceptance timeframe. Procurement processes and approaches achieve such objectives by clearly defining what is liable to take any risk that cannot be eliminated from the project and providing adequate and reliable information on the work to be carried out so that all concerned stakeholders understand what to be done and their role to that effect. Therefore, procurement is more concerned with the purchase or acquisition of goods or services through competitive biddings in a manner that is transparent and accountability. It is the series of processes that are essential to get products or services from requisition to purchase order and invoice approval.

Public procurement processes and approaches include activities and events before and after the signing of a contract as well as the general management activities associated with a range of contracts: Precontract activities such as planning, needs identification and analysis, and sourcing; Post-contract activities such as contract management, supply chain management and disposal, and; General activities such as corporate governance, supplier relationship management, risk management and regulatory compliance. The approach that has been taken for many years within the public sector can be summarized as follows: purchasing should be based on value for money, competition should be used to acquire goods and services (unless there are convincing reasons to the contrary); there should be clear definition of the roles and responsibilities of personnel involved in

specifying the need giving financial authority making procurement commitments; there should be a separation of the financial authority and the purchase authority; there should be a separation of duties between personnel who makes the contracts, those who receive goods or services and those who oath payments; and requirements which are above a certain financial threshold are normally required to be advertised in accordance with regulations on public procurement (Bailey et al, 2008).

Morris (2003) emphasizes that in procurement process, it is important to define the product or service required first, then the selection supplier. Cousins et al, (2008) argue that strategic supplier selection involves four main stages: initial supplier qualification; agree measurement criteria obtain relevant information and make selection. Supplier qualification is the first step towards supplier selection. The goal is to identify suppliers who meet the requisite product and process standards and are capable of supporting the buyer's long-term objectives. Because organizations are resource constrained, qualification helps to reduce the pool of potential suppliers to a more manageable number for detailed evaluation and selection (Cousin et al, 2008). Poterba (2001) emphasizes that evaluating suppliers is one of the most critical functions of a purchasing manager, buyer, or purchasing agent.

The one credible procedure in the process of selecting suppliers or contractors is the solicitation of bids which are usually advertised stating the needs, minimum standard qualifications and details of the project, product or services. Thai, (2004), maintained that it is a useful tool which call for competition and provide suppliers and contractors or bidders with sufficient information. A solicitation is a process of notifying prospective or qualified bidder that an organization wishes to receive bids or proposals on the specified product or service through a solicitation document placed in advert. A solicitation document is a formalization of this process in a written format. Solicitations include request for pricing, Invitation for Bid (IFB), and Request for Proposals (RFP), which may be required to be made public through advertising, mailings, or some other method of communication. Solicitation documents will vary greatly depending on the procurement method chosen. Regardless of procurement method all solicitation documents should contain enough information to permit the potential bidder to submit an adequate response.

Section 17 of the Public Procurement Act as stated in section 7.1 of the Procurement Procedures Manual for Public Procurement in Nigeria states that "A Notice Board, located in a public area must be maintained for the public posting of procurement notices and solicitations. The following actions are posted on the Notice Board: Requests for Proposals

(RFPs) - RFPs must also be advertised in at least two National newspapers of general circulation – and the Federal Tender's Journal; Invitations for Bids (IFB); Single source determinations, and; Emergency determinations. If the procuring entity maintains an internet web site, that web site should contain a page on which the above information is also posted. Section 41.4 provided that every advert of an invitation to an Open Competitive Bid shall include: The name and address of the procuring entity; The nature, quantity, category and place of delivery of goods to be procured or the nature, category, and location of the works to be procured; A statement that submissions must be made only in the English language; The deadline for delivering or performing the procurement; Information about the requirements to be met by suppliers and contractors; A statement of the application of domestic preferences if any; The instructions for obtaining the documents containing the specifications of the essential provisions of the procurement and the price, if any, for these documents; The place and deadline for the submission of the bids; The place, date and time for the opening of the bids. It is generally stated that timely appropriate notification of procurement opportunities for goods, works and consulting services is essential for economic and efficient project execution, and is the basis for eliciting maximum competition with fair opportunities for all potential bidders (Federal Republic of Nigeria, Procurement Procedures Manual for Public Procurement in Nigeria, Bureau of Public Procurement (BPP), 2011).

Ultimately, all procurement of goods and services process requires the procuring entity to predefine or specify its needs and requirements, set the criteria for their supply, and offer every interested bidder equal and simultaneous information and opportunity to offer the goods, services, and works needed. Such invitations to bid can either be by way of National Competitive Bidding (NCB) or international competitive bidding (ICB), depending on the monetary threshold set by the Bureau.

Table 1: Advertisement requirements of NCB and ICB as provided in the Act.

Methods	Advert Media	Time of Advert
International Competitive Bidding (ICB)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • at least 2 national dailies • one relevant internationally recognized publication • Official website of procuring entity • Official website of BPP 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not less than 6 weeks from deadline for submission of bids

- National Competitive Bidding
- Notice board of procuring entity
 - Official website of procuring entity
 - at least 2 national dailies
 - procurement journal
- Not less than 6 weeks from deadline for submission of bids

Empirical Review

Ogunsanmi (2013) assessed the effect of procurement related factors on construction project performance in Nigeria. The study revealed specifically that procurement selection criteria, tendering methods and variation orders have impact on project performance. Muhammad, Adamu, and Ladi (2015) opine that the success of performance of public sector projects in Nigeria is tied to the impact of procurement strategy or policy used in providing the building. Thus, it is not gainsaying that implementation of a public procurement policy is vital to secure best value for public money. Bodunrin, (2016) stated that procurement has always been one of the vital functions of governments all over the world, with the basic purpose of which is to secure best value for public money. It is a catalyst to transparency, accountability, efficiency, and value for money (Florence, 2018; Manu, et.al 2018).

Ojo and Gbadabo (2014) assessed the non-compliance with procurement proceedings in procurement of works in Nigeria, using the mean score ranking they were able to establish areas/stage and reasons for non-compliance. Significant bid open/evaluation and reporting, procurement procedure, and political party or authority influence of decisions are significant. Nwogwugwu and Adebayo (2015) and Akinseye (2016) are of the view that the enactment of the Public procurements Act 2007, has not still either ensured integrity, accountability, or transparency in public procurements in Nigeria. However, Akinseye (2016) buttressed that the problem is not with the Act. As there were adequate implementation strategies of the Bureau established for the purpose of the procurement policy. Musa, Ejura and Nwaorgu (2014) affirmed the position that the problem is not the inadequacy of a regulatory framework but rather that of poor implementation and non-compliance with the reforms laws and regulations. Bodunrin, (2016) stated that the existence of multiple procurement guidelines and procedures, overt emphasis on procurement of manpower, the fear of vigilance, poor/quality training and lack of centralized data sharing facility etc. were the challenges and problems of effective public procurement practices in Nigeria. In the same line Ekwo (2013) pointed out among others

that the wide discretionary powers of procurement officers under the direction of management emerged as possible risk factors motivating corruption in the public procurement process thus making the process vulnerable to corruption. This tend to indicate that there were corruption in the actual implementation process. Florence (2018), indicated lack of structures and facilities to ease procurement process and pervading corruption in Nigeria as factors that have hindered the full implementation of the Act.

Akinseye (2016) findings corroborated the challenges, highlighting; political patronage, corruption, poor technical knowledge of procurement, inability to prosecute procurement offenders and lack of political will on the part of government as the challenges that affects the implementation of public procurement policy in Nigeria. These factors were not different from the general problems that have bedeviled public policy implementation in Nigeria. In conclusion, the findings goes to show that there is problem with the implementation process of the Public procurement Act, 2007. This situation is not peculiar to Nigeria, as studies from Ghana by Frempong, Bempah, Amoako, and Osei-Tutu (2013) on an assessment of the impact of the public procurement act 663 (2003) of the republic of Ghana, revealed that there were difficulties associated with public procurement, which include difficulties in applying and implementing the Act, lack of usage flexibility, lack of authority to dispose public assets, the lack of independent procurement auditing function, no central body with technical expertise and also threshold are too small for entities like a district assembly in case of emergency situation.

From the review it is evident that enough work has been done on the area of assessing the challenges and factors affecting the implementation of the Public Procurement Act, 2007, but no specific study has been conducted to determine the extent of compliance on the specific process and guideline of advertisement for solicitation of bids by the Federal Ministry of Education Federal Ministry of Education. Thus, there is a gap in knowledge in this area as most of the studies addressed on a general perspective on the challenges of the implementation of the Act. It was observed that most of the study adopted the use of questionnaire to gather the data which could face the problem of bias, but this study intends use observation which is less affected by bias. Also, since observation made by the SGF that publication for solicitation of bids in Federal Tender Journal and National Dallies by most MDAs of Federal Government exhibit poor compliance with the standard requirement for the solicitation of bids as stipulated in Section 16(6) of the Public Procurement Act, 2007 published in Circular Ref. No. 59858/S.11/VOL.II/332 of 18th May, 2018. It is observed that no published study from the review conducted has been done on the subject matter. Thus, this study will provide currency and framework for further studies.

Theoretical Framework

The system theory gives more insight to the nature of procurement process. Procurement process is a supply chain management process, as 'supply chain management' is a term that has been used to reflect a variety of different meanings, which procurement is part of. (Harland, 1996). Supply chains are considered to be systems, the current research study aims at casting light on the advertisement and solicitation of bids in the procurement process as a sub-system in the whole system process of public procurement. gained from the application of the general systems theory to supply chains and their management.

The application of general systems theory, as developed by Boulding (1956), Forrester (1958, 1961, 1975); von Bertalanffy (1969), generally recognized as the founding father of general systems theory; Klir (1969, 1972); Weinberg (1975); Miller (1978), and Yourdon (1989) are discussed. The adoption of the general systems theory is spurred by the integration of different processes and approaches to public procurement decision making mechanisms as also seen in supply chain modelling (Chopra and Meindl, 2004; Christopher, 2005; Li, Kumar and Lim, 2002). For instance, Mourits and Evers (1995) discuss the several stages or echelons relating to the flow of goods between a supplier and a customer in current distribution networks. Each stage may be comprised of many processes, and facilitates different activities, thus, necessitating the intensive network and communication as a system for their mutual co-ordination. This is, the defining characteristic of public procurement process as the implementation of one process facilitates and aids the next process. Thus, a failure or poor implementation of one process will definitely affect the implementation of the other. As it is stated in the SGF Circular Ref. No. 59858/S.11/VOL.II/332 of 18th May, 2018 that the exhibition of poor compliance with the standard requirement in bid solicitations reviewed by BPP has resulted in frequent corrections by the BPP which affects the Standard Processing Time of procurement in the MDAs resulting in project delays.

Methodology

This research utilized survey and analysis of existing data research design method. The study relied mainly on primary data. The primary data was collected through the use of observation checklist and questionnaire developed by the researcher. The population is the contractors, consultants and service providers of the Federal Ministry of Education Headquarters' projects, goods and services, staff of the BPP and Civil Society Organizations into procurement and budget monitoring in Nigeria. The population may be finite, but it is not possible to identify all its members. Contractors, consultants and service providers of the Federal Ministry of Education are particularly problematic to

identify, given that the BPP is yet to compile a database and publish a register of federal contractors, consultants and service providers as required by the Act. These attributes predisposed the study to use purposive and convenience sampling techniques to select the actual sample. The researcher used the Secretariat of the Federal Ministry of Education to distribute questionnaire to the Ministries contractors, consultants and service providers. 400 copies of the questionnaire were produced for them. The number of questionnaires returned formed the population of contractors, consultants, and service providers. The list of CSOs into procurement and budget monitoring was pulled from the coalition of National Procurement Watch Platform Framework Document, as provided by Public and Private Development Centre (PPDC) that developed a Public Procurement Watch Program. The list is shown in Table 1.2 below

Table 2: List of Selected Sample for CSOs into Procurement and Budget Monitoring in Nigeria

CSOs into Procurement and Budget Monitoring in Nigeria	
1	Public and Private Development Centre (PPDC)
2	Civil Society Legislative Advocacy Centre (CISLAC)
3	Kudirat Initiative for Democracy (KIND)
4	Civil Society Network Against Corruption (CSNAC)
5	Socio-Economic Right and Accountability Project (SERAP)
6	Zero-Corruption Coalition (ZCC)
7	Policy and Legal Advocacy Centre (PLAC),
8	Public Interest Lawyers League (PILL)
9	WANGONET and Community Action For Popular Participation.
10	The National Procurement Watch Platform

The staff of the Bureau of Public Procurement were selected from the Compliance, Certification and Monitoring (CCandM) department. This was necessary because one of their functions is to vet advertisements to ensure compliance with the Public Procurement Act (PPA), 2007. They are 15 in number as 2020 and all were selected (Bureau of Public Procurement 2019 Annual Report). The total number of respondents were 400, composed of: Contractors, Consultants and Service providers – 85, Civil Society Organizations – 300 and; Bureau of Public Procurement Staff – 15.

The researcher organized the data collected from the questionnaire and presents it using tabular form of descriptive statistics as it relates to the research questions, where the numbers of data to each response options will be computed to the rating scale classification

in statistical criteria. It will then be analyzed using percentages and mean rating. For proper presentations a bar chart will be used to present the percentage responses, while highlighting its frequency.

Result and Findings

The data collected through the questionnaire and observation checklist were collated, and the analysis of the question statement and indices observed that were related to the research questions were used to answer the research questions. The summary analysis of the responses to the questionnaire were presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Summary of Responses and Analysis to the Questionnaire on the Level of Compliance with the Advertisement for Solicitation of Bid Guidelines

Statement Questions	Response Options										Mean Rating
	Yes		No		If Yes, to what extent						
	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	Large Extent		Moderate Extent		Low Extent		
	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	
1 Do the Ministry have a Notice Board for the public posting of procurement notices and solicitations	391	98	09	02	391	100	-	-	-	-	3.00
2 Do the Ministry regularly post procurement notices and solicitations for its procurement for the public on the Notice Board	181	45	219	55	21	12	150	83	10	05	2.06
3 Do the Ministry regularly maintain the Notice Board by removing irrelevant posts and materials from it	309	77	91	23	101	33	166	54	42	13	2.19
4 Do the Ministry regularly maintain the Notice Board by ensuring that the procurement notices were not removed by unauthorized personnel	231	58	169	42	151	65	71	31	09	04	2.61
5 Do all the notices of procurement and solicitation of bids of the Ministry allowed to stay its due time for publication on the Notice Board.	391	98	09	02	300	77	91	23	-	-	2.76

Do the Ministry place advertisement in at least two

6	National general circulation the newspapers of 361 [√] 90 45 - 2.55 Request for Proposal procurements Do the Ministry's advertisement for Proposal (RFPs)	39 10 55 (RFPs)	200			161	-
			251	for its			03
		Request placed	380	for			-
7	in the National newspapers 300 [√] 75 09 2.80 provided all the information for bid solicitation regul arly Ministry's advertisement for Proposal (RFPs)	100 25 needed	16	84 40	13		51
		Do the	380				-
		Request placed	381	for			-
			02				37
8	in the National newspapers 400 100 approved by the Editorial Board of BPP placements Do the Ministry's advertisement for Proposal (RFP s)	- - 95 before	-	20 05 -	2.95		-
			181				06
		Request placed	300	for			02

6	in the National newspapers	280 70	120 30	06	121 43	143 1.54	
	have no error that necessitated an addendum to correct it						
	Do the Ministry place advertisement in the Federal						
7	Tender's Journal the Request	400 100	-- 95	20 05	-2.95		
	for Proposal (RFP) regularly for its procurement						
8	Do the Ministry have an official website	400 100	-- 95	19 05	-2.95		
	Do the Ministry's official website have a portal or						
9	column clearly stated for	✓ 19 05	381 95	10	10 53	07 1.73	
	procurement notices or advert						
	Do the Ministry place its						
10	procurement advert for bid solicitation or Request for	--			400 --	-- ✓ -0.00	
	Proposal on its website						
	Do the organization place its						
11	procurement advert for bid solicitation or Request for	298 74	102 26	61	100 33		
	172.55						
	Proposal on the BPP website Do the Ministry submit its						
12	advertisements for solicitation of bids to the	398 99	02 01	75 90 23	08 2.73		
	Editorial Board of the						
	Federal Tender Journals by the mandatory time						

Source: Calculations of Data from Field Study (Questionnaire) (2021).

Research Question I: To what extent has the Federal Ministry of Education complied with maintaining of Notice Board for the public posting of procurement notices and solicitations?

The item question 1 – 4 in the questionnaire as summarized in Table 1.3 above relates to this question. It revealed that 98% of the respondents indicated that the Ministry do have a notice board for the public posting of procurement notices and solicitations and all of them agreed to this to a large extent, having a mean rating of 3.00 out of 3.00. The Ministry do not just have the notice boards but it was observed from the responses that 77%, 58% and 98% indicated that the Ministry regularly maintain the notice board by removing irrelevant posts and materials from it; ensured regularly that the procurement notices were not removed by unauthorized personnel; and that all the notices of procurement and solicitation of bids were allowed to stay its due time for publication on the notice board respectively. However, 55% of the respondents indicated that the Ministry do not regularly post procurement notices and solicitations for its procurement for the public on the notice

board. This negates the principle behind having the notice board, as the Ministry is expected to paste or publish all notices relating to the procurement on the board, not only the advert for the solicitation of bids as it was observed.

This findings is also in line with the observation made by the researcher. The researcher saw he notice board of the Ministry and in it there were notices of solicitation of bids as published in the Federal Government Tender Journals. A bar chart in Figure 1 below is used to give a graphical representation of the percentages of the responses to the question.

Figure 1: Bar Chart Showing the Percentage Responses on the Ministry's Use of Notice Board for Public Posting of Procurement Notices and Solicitations of Bids

Research Question II: To what extent has Federal Ministry of Education comply with placing of advertisement in at least two National newspapers of general circulation and the Federal Tender's Journal the Request for Proposal (RFPs)?

The item question 6 – 10 in the questionnaire as summarized in Table 1.3 above relates to this question. It indicated in item question 6, that 90% of the respondents answer that the Ministry place advertisement in at least two National newspapers of general circulation its Request for Proposal (RFPs) for its procurements. It goes to show that the 90% of respondents that answered Yes to the question, 55% of them asserted that this was done to a

large extent, while 45% said to a moderate extent. This gave a meaning rating of 2.55 which is above the grand mean of 2.00. The similar pattern, in item question 10, all the respondents indicated that the Ministry publishes its Request for Proposal (RFPs) for its procurements in the Federal Tender's Journal. This means that it maintain a 100% affirmation on the compliance. Responses to item question 7, 8 and 9 indicated that the placement of the advertisement follows the stipulated guidelines as 75% of the respondents answered 'Yes' that the Ministry's advertisement for Request for Proposal (RFPs) placed in the National newspapers do provide all the needed information for bid solicitation, 100% of the respondents answered 'Yes' that Ministry's advertisement for Request for Proposal (RFPs) placed in the National newspapers were approved by the Editorial Board of BPP before placements. However, 70% of the respondents answered 'Yes' that the Ministry's advertisement for Request for Proposal (RFPs) placed in the National newspapers sometimes have some error that necessitated an addendum to correct it. This is raised a serious concern as to who is responsible for error, as it is earlier stated in item question 8 that Request for Proposal (RFPs) placed in the National newspapers were usually approved by the Editorial Board of BPP before placements. It could mean that the Editorial Board of the BPP may not have taken due diligence to correct the error or refer back to the Ministry to correct it. Probably, they were under pressure by the Ministry or other interested government official to publish it, so as to quickly dispense the projects or procurements.

This finding as indicated in item question 9 looking at the Ministry's Tender for 2020, the researcher observed that there were quite a number of 'Addendum' to the Tender for the execution of the 2020 Appropriation. One of them reads:

“Addendum - Re: Invitation to Tender for Execution of 2020 Appropriation. The Federal Ministry of Education wishes to draw the attention of prospective Bidders and General Public to the Ministry's Advertisement in the Daily Trust and Tribune Newspapers of Monday 9th March, 2020 and the Federal Tender Journal of Monday 9th – Sunday March 22nd 2020 Vol. 16 No. 5.” (<https://www.bpp.gov.ng/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/Ministry-of-Education-Advert-ADDENDUM.pdf>)

The researcher also observed as it relates to item question 7; The Ministry's advertisement for Request for Proposal (RFPs) placed in the National newspapers do provide all the needed information for bid solicitation. It is noted that not all the Tender provides all the needed information as given in the guideline and format provided by Bureau of Public Procurement (BPP) through the Office of the Secretary to the Government of the Federation

(SGF) in its Circular with reference: Ref.No.59858/S.11/VOL.II/332. It was observed that the background of the Ministry's objective and the projects or service is usually missing or not adequate. Also, the heading of scope of works/supply are usually not provided. This is in contrast with the directives of the BPP, But what is appalling is that the BPP still go ahead to publish the Tender in its website, thereby giving approval.

Research Question III: To what extent has Federal Ministry of Education comply with placing advertisement in their official website and BPP website the Request for Proposal (RFPs)?

The item question 11 – 14 in the questionnaire as summarized in Table 1.3 above relates to this question. It showed in item question 11, that 100% of the respondents indicated that the Ministry has an official website. However, 95% and 100% of the respondents revealed that the Ministry's website has no portal or column clearly stated for procurement notices; and the Ministry do not place advert for bid solicitation or RFPs on its website, respectively. Going further 74% of the respondents answered 'Yes' that the Ministry place its procurement or Tender advert on the BPP website. This is further represented in Figure 2 below

Figure 2: Bar Chart showing the Frequency Responses on the Ministry's placing of its Advert for Bids Solicitations on its Official Website and the BPP Website

It is emphatic that no respondent answered 'Yes' to the Ministry placing its advert for bids solicitation on its website. The researcher observed that the Ministry has a website with a web address as <https://education.gov.ng/#>. The website has a procurement page stated under department page of the website with an address as <https://education.gov.ng/procurement/>. But when it is clicked on, it indicated that the page is under construction, as no information is yet uploaded as at the time of this research. Also, in the BBP website the Ministry's Tenders were seen by the researcher. Based on this it is clear in terms of the provision of the Act and its guideline manual the Ministry is yet to comply with the publication of its Tender on its website. This could be accounted by the fact that the websites were built earlier without provision for the procurement page, and to rebuild the website requires another appropriation for it and which is usually not too easy to get, as quick as possible in Ministries because of the bureaucratic process it will require to get it approved and done.

Research Question IV: To what extent has Federal Ministry of Education comply with the required format of advertisements for solicitation of bids submitted to the Editorial Board of the Federal Tender Journals?

The item question 7 – 9, and 15 in the questionnaire as summarized in Table 1.3 above relates to this question. As earlier indicated in research question II, which shows that 75% of the respondents which is the majority of the respondent clearly indicated in item question 9; that the Ministry's advertisement for Request for Proposal (RFPs) placed in the National newspapers sometimes have some error that necessitated an addendum to correct it. This result is placing a question on the findings in item question 15, which 98% of the respondents indicated that the Ministry do submit its advertisements for solicitation of bids to the Editorial Board of the Federal Tender Journals by the mandatory time. The question is them, if they do submit their advertisements for solicitation of bids to the Editorial Board whose responsibility is to vet it to ensure it conform to the requirement or guideline provided by the BPP. Why then are there still errors which necessitates addendum. In another argument, it could be said that the Editorial Board of the Federal Tender Journal only vet what they were given and that some of the addendums were mainly missing information. If this could be, the researcher observed that some of the published Tender still not comply with the guideline as provided by the Bureau of Public Procurement (BPP) through the Office of the Secretary to the Government of the Federation (SGF) in its Circular with reference: Ref.No.59858/S.11/VOL.II/332.

Based on these observations and results the following findings were made:

- i. The Federal Ministry of Education to large extent complied with maintaining of Notice Board for the public posting of procurement notices and solicitations, but to the extent of posting regularly its procurement notices and solicitations for its procurement for the public on the notice board is still in question.
- ii. The Federal Ministry of Education to a moderate extent complied with placing of advertisement in at least two National newspapers of general circulation and the Federal Tender's Journal the Request for Proposal (RFPs).
- iii. The Federal Ministry of Education to a large extent complied with placing advertisement on the BPP website the RFPs, but did not comply with placing advertisement on their official website the Request for Proposal (RFPs)
- iv. The Federal Ministry of Education to a low extent complied with the required format of advertisements for solicitation of bids submitted to the Editorial Board of the Federal Tender Journals.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusion are drawn. It is evident that the Federal Ministry of Education has made some improvement in the advertisement process of its procurement. But the format for drafting a RFPs is still not complied with. This would probably necessitate delay in the procurement process and extra cost for publications of addendums. Also, a lot need to be done in terms of building a functional webpage in their website for procurement notices. Ultimately, the advertisement process of the Ministry's procurement is still not up to the desired expectations. In the light of thus, the following recommendations should be taken to address the situation:

- i. The Federal Ministry of Education and other MDAs should build or rebuild its functional website to carry a webpage for its procurement matters and notices as required by the BPP Procurement Procedures and Manual.
- ii. The BBP should conduct a capacity training of its staff and staff of the Federal Ministry of Education and other MDAs on how draft RFPs following the guidelines provided by the BPP. vii. The BPP Editorial Board should restructure the time for the submission of advertisement for solicitation of bids to be submitted to the Federal Tender Journal to give them sufficient time to vet and refer back to the Ministries before publications.
- iii. Strict compliance to the guidelines should be implemented. The BPP should come

up with penalty or sanctions for MDAs and its Directors that did not comply with the guidelines.

References

- Adebiyi, A. A., Ayo, C. K. and Adebiyi M O. (2010). Development of Electronic Government Procurement (e-GP) System for Nigeria Public Sector. *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Sciences* 10(6); 68–77
- Adewole, A. (2014). Governance Reform and the Challenge of Implementing Public Procurement Law Regime across Nigerian State and Local Governments. *International Journal of Public Administration and Management Research* 2(4); 25–32
- Akinseye, R. A. (2016). An Assessment of the Implementation of Public Procurement Policy in Nigeria. A Thesis Submitted to the Department of Public Administration, Faculty of Administration, in Partial Fulfilment of the Requirements for the Award of The Degree of Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D) in Public Administration, of the Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife.
- Ameyaw, C., Mensah, S. and Osei-Tutu, E. (2012). Public Procurement in Ghana: The Implementation Challenges to the Public Procurement Law 2000 (Act 663). *International Journal of Construction Supply Chain Management*, 2(2), 55–65.
- Arrowsmith S, Treumer S, Fejo J, and Jiang L (2011). *Public Procurement Regulation: An Introduction* University of Nottingham, EUROPEAID Co-operation Office.
- Arrowsmith, S. and Trybus, M. (2003) *Public Procurement: the Continuing Revolution*. The Hague, New York: Kluwer Law International.
- Baily, P., David F., Barry, C., Jossop, D. and Jones, D. (2008). *Procurement Principles and Management*. (9thEd.). Person Education Limited, England.
- Bodunrin, A. K. (2016). Empirical Review and Analysis of Public Procurement Practices in Nigeria: Challenges and Prospects. *Public Policy and Administration Research* 6(3); 128–135
- Bovis C. H. (2007). European Union Public Procurement Law. *Elgar European Law Series*, Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Chartered Institute of Purchasing and Supply (CIPS), (2012). *Sustainability in Supply Chains*. Lincolnshire: Prose publishing.
- Cronbach, L. J. (1951). Coefficient Alpha and the Internal Structure of Tests. *Psychometrika*, 16(3), 297–333.
- Ekwo, G. A. U. (2013). Corruption Risk Factors: An Analysis of Public Procurement in Nigeria. A Thesis Submitted in Partial Fulfilment of the Requirements of the University of Northumbria at Newcastle for the Degree of Doctor of Business

Administration

- Emmett, S. and Crocker, B. (2008). *Excellence in Procurement*. Cambridge Academic: Gt. Sheldford, Cambridge.
- Ezekwesili, O. (2002). Integrating the Due Process Principle into the Budget Process. A Paper Presented at a Seminar on Implementing the 2002 Budget, 3rd – 5th April 2002, in Enugu.
- Familoye, O., Ogunsemi, D. R. and Awodele, O. A. (2016). Assessment of the Challenges Facing the Effective Operations of the Nigeria Public Procurement Act 2007. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management United Kingdom* 3(11); 957 – 967
- Fayomi, I.O. (2013). Public Procurement and Due Process Policy in Nigeria: Thrust, Prospects and Challenges. *Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities* 1(4); 39 – 45.
- Federal Government of Nigeria. (2007) *Public Procurement Act*. Lagos, Nigeria: The Federal Government Printer.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2011), *Procurement Procedures Manual for Public Procurement in Nigeria*. 2nd (Ed.) Published by Bureau of Public Procurement (BPP)
- Florence, F. O. (2018). Implementation of Public Procurement Act and Government Performance: Evidence from Nigeria. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 1(4); 1 – 9.
- Frempong, R. K., Bempah, G. O., Amoako, D., and Osei-Tutu, S. T. (2013). An Assessment of the Impact of the Public Procurement Act 663 (2003) of the Republic of Ghana, Approaching a Decade of its Enactment. *Public Policy and Administration Research*, 3(2), 62-69
- Jacob, O. A. (2010). Procurement Law in Nigeria: Challenge for Attainment of its Objectives. *University of Botswana Law Journal*. Chapter 6
- Lysons, K. and Farrington, B. (2006). *Purchasing and Supply Chain Management*. (7th Ed.). Prentice Hall.
- Manu, P, Mahamadu, A, Booth, C., Olomolaiye, P., Ibrahim, A and Coker, A. (2018). Assessment of Procurement Capacity Challenges Inhibiting Public Infrastructure Procurement: A Nigerian Inquiry. *Built Environment Project and Asset Management*,
- Muhammad, B. A., Adamu, T., and Ladi B. D. (2015). Appraisal of Construction Project Procurement Policies in Nigeria. *American Journal of Engineering Research*, 4(3); 19 – 24
- Musa, S. J., Ejura. B. S. and Nwaorgu, I. A. (2014). The Public Procurement Reforms in Nigeria: Implementation and Compliance Challenges. *Journal of Asian Business Strategy*, 4(11); 149 – 162
- Nash, R. J., Cibnic, J. J., Ralph, C., and Nagle, J. F. (2006). *Administration of Government*

Contract (4th Ed.). Washington DC: George Washington University, Walter Kluwer Law and Business.

Nwogwugwu, N. and Adebayo, A. O (2015). Appraisal of Integrity in Public Procurement Processes in Nigeria *Journal of Business and Management*. 17(7); 110 – 115

Ogunsanmi, O. E. (2013). Effects of Procurement Related Factors on Construction Project. *Ethiopian Journal of Environmental Studies and Management*, 6(2), 215 – 222

Pratyush, S. (2009). Enhancing Value in Public Procurement. *International Journal of Project Management*, 24(1),

Public and Private Development Centre (PPDC) (2011). Implementing the Nigerian procurement law: Compliance with the Public Procurement Act, 2007 A Surveys of Procuring Entities, Civil Society Observers, Bidders and Contractors, Legislators and the bureau of public procurement

Thai, K. V. (2004) *Challenges in Public Procurement*. In International Handbook of Public Procurement. 1-20. Florida: Academics Press.